

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 27, No. 9

Dear Readers,

Welcome to the ninth issue in 2021. I am very pleased to mention that the access statistics show a steady growth and also the interest in our journal is increasing. This success is only possible because of the great support from all of you. Thus, on behalf of the J.UCS team, I would like to thank all authors for their sound research contributions, the reviewers for their very helpful suggestions, and the consortium members for their financial support. Your commitment and dedicated work have contributed significantly to the overall success of J.UCS.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to present three accepted papers from five different countries and 10 involved authors.

Armando Cruz, Hugo Paredes, Leonel Morgado and Paulo Martins from Portugal investigate in their work non-verbal aspects of collaboration in virtual worlds in the context of the presence dimension. In a collaborative research between Chile and Japan, Paul Leger, Hiroaki Fukuda and Ismael Figueroa present a JavaScript package that allows developers to write event handlers that need nested callbacks in a synchronous style, avoiding the so-called 'callback hell'. In another collaboration between Indonesia and the UK, Riri Fitri Sari, Asri Samsiar Ilmananda, and Daniela M. Romano discuss their research on a social trust-based blockchain-enabled social media news verification system.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

Christian Gütl, Managing Editor
Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
Email: c.guetl@tugraz.at